

THE USE OF LITERATURE IN THE LANGUAGE CLASSROOM

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Annotation: Literature and language are closely related and this is a fact none can deny. Literature is constituted by language and it represents one of the most recurrent uses of language.

Language and linguistic analysis can also be employed to access literature from the learner’s point of view. Brumfit and Carter already emphasized the role of literature as —an ally of language. This technique is by no means novel, since literature has been a widely used teaching tool in different language teaching methods. However, here the perspective changes giving more relevance to the literary text as a work of art.

Literary texts of the target language were read and translated, used as examples of good writing and —illustrations of the grammatical rules. The focus of this teaching method was on form, on learning the rules of grammar and the lexical items as they appeared in the text. There was no literary interest, nor interest on content. After this method fell in disuse, literary texts also went forgotten for teachers of second languages. For the structural approaches to language teaching, literature was discredited as a tool, because it represented the old tradition. The functional-notional method ignored literature, because in this method the importance lies on communication and they present authentic language samples. Literature was not considered either to have a communicative function or to be authentic example of language use. Nonetheless, in the last decade or so the interest in literature as one of the most valuable language teaching resources available has revived remarkably. Language and linguistic analysis can also be employed to access literature from the learner’s point of

view. Brimful and Carter already emphasized the role of literature as —an ally of language. This technique is by no means novel, since literature has been a widely used teaching tool in different language teaching methods. However, here the perspective changes giving more relevance to the literary text as a work of art. First of all, let us go over the changing role of literature in the tradition of second language teaching to end with an account of its current situation within the communicative approach. In the grammar translation method, literature was the central component.

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Our response to the cultural aspect as reflected in literature should be critical. The motivational criterion is of great relevance because the literary text shows the real feelings of the writer and this generates a powerful motivation in the learner. With the literary text the student accesses this personal experience, if she is touched by the theme and provoked, she will be able to relate what she is reading to her world, to what she knows and feels. Designing stimulating activities that motivate the learners is the greatest challenge for language teachers, and literature has a strong motivating power due to its calling on to personal experience.

The purpose of using literature in a language classroom is to make the class interactive and it can be stated that an interactive class can obviously improve communicative competence of the learners and keep a lasting impact on their mind. Such a class can enhance the critical thinking abilities of the learners and at the same time maintain a learner centre environment. Literary texts are a rich source of classroom activities and can surely prove to be very motivating for learners. No wonder the use of literary pieces play a significant role in English Language Teaching. Literature opens a new world to the students. It cultivates the critical abilities of the students. It encompasses every human dilemma, conflict and yearning unraveling the plot of a short story is more than an automatic exercise.

It demands a personal response from the learners and encourages them draw on their own experiences. By doing so, learners become more personally invested in the process of language learning. The use of literature is to focus on the positive contributions of a literary text as it exposes the learner to different registers, types of language use. An attractive and enjoyable short story that conveys our feeling or emotion can touch the learner's heart instantly.

Consequently, the language class becomes not only exciting but also it reciprocates with impulsiveness and interest. This genuineness in learning leaves a lasting impact on the students' mind. The dialogic nature of literary pieces paves the way for individual learner's response to a particular piece of literature that ensures his or her use of creative faculty, of course through language. Such learning drives away the monotony of traditional language classes. Thus, it gives the teacher an opportunity to open a broad context of language use for the students.

Three main reasons for the teaching of literature have been consistently advanced. Each embraces a particular set of learning objectives for the student. These are:

- 1) The cultural model
- 2) The language model

3) The personal growth model

The models may be summarized as follows:

A. The Cultural Model

Teachers working within such an orientation stress the value of literature in encapsulating the accumulated wisdom, the best that has been thought and felt within a culture.

Through literature students get to know the background not only of the particular novel but also they learn about history, society, and politics of the country described in the novel or story. By experiencing this, they open themselves to understanding and appreciating ideologies, mentalities, traditions, feeling, and artistic form within the heritage the literature of such cultures endows.

B. The Language Model

One of the main reasons for a teacher's orientation towards a language model for teaching literature is to give students knowledge with some sense of the more subtle and varied creative uses of language. A main impulse of language-centered literature teaching is to help students find ways into a text in a methodical way and for themselves. If we take into consideration that —*literature is made from language* (Boas), we can easily conclude that if students can improve their reading abilities they will be able to come to terms with a literary text as literature.

C. The personal Growth Model

Teachers are very interested in the personal growth model of the students. Teachers' main goal is to help students achieve an *engagement* with the reading of literary texts (Boas). Helping students to read literature more effectively is helping them to grow and mature as individuals as well as their relationships with the people around them. To encourage personal growth the teacher has to select texts to which students can respond and to which they can use their ideas and imagination creatively.

So teachers have to use literature more often in their lessons and extracurricular lessons in order to motivate learners to learn foreign languages.

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